

Lesson Study as a Vehicle to Foster Teacher Agency

Mairéad Holden

School of Education, University of Lincoln, United Kingdom

The evidence in support of Lesson Study (LS) as a powerful approach to Teacher Professional Development (PD) continues to grow at a rapid rate. However, despite its widespread popularity, the mechanisms by which LS fosters teacher agency remain under-theorised. In order to address this theoretical gap, this paper proposes an emergent theoretical framework which seeks to explain how LS may foster teachers' achievement of agency. The paper describes how this framework derived from a systematic review of literature, which drew from a total of 32 empirical studies across a range of contexts. Guided by an ecological conceptualisation of teacher agency, a process of thematic analysis on data from studies allowed identification of a number of agency enablers, linked to LS activities. These links are used to generate an emergent theoretical framework, which holds relevance for researchers, LS facilitators, practitioners and policymakers. The timeliness of such a framework is notable given the recent publication of the draft Primary Curriculum Framework (NCCA, 2020), which espouses the importance of teacher agency in order to realise its aim of supporting children to achieve their full potential.

Introduction

The teaching profession in Ireland, like those in many jurisdictions, currently finds itself in a swiftly flowing river of educational change across both primary and post-primary sectors. The STEM subject disciplines have experienced an especially rapid flow of change across policy and curricula (DES, 2016; NCCA, 2020). STEM, which refers not simply to Science, Technology, Engineering and Maths, but a cross-curricular approach focusing on activities relevant to all four areas (Rosicka, 2016) does not exist as a standalone subject within the current Irish Primary Curriculum. This presents a challenge for generalist Irish primary teachers, who are expected to deliver effective integrated STEM teaching and learning experiences within mathematics and science (DES, 2016). Preparations are underway for a redeveloped primary curriculum, which aims to support a more authentic integrated approach to teaching and learning in all subjects, including the STEM disciplines (NCCA, 2020). In order to operationalise such changes in a way which most benefits outcomes for learners, Irish primary teachers require support in the form of professional learning opportunities which foster their achievement of agency (Darling-Hammond, 2005; NCCA, 2020). One school-based Professional Development (PD) approach which appears to offer promise in this regard is Lesson Study (LS) (Dudley et al., 2019; Ní Shuilleabháin & Seery, 2018). However, the means by which LS operates to support teachers' potential achievement of agency remains insufficiently theorised (Schipper et al., 2020). In order to address this theoretical gap, the researcher sought to answer the question: How and in what circumstances can Lesson Study enhance teacher agency in STEM and in the primary setting? This paper describes the process of how that question was addressed by a systematic review of existing LS literature, focusing on findings relating to agency enablers. The review process used an ecological conceptualisation of agency (Priestly et al., 2015) to identify and analyse possible connections between LS and teachers' achievement of agency in previous empirical studies,

particularly in the area of primary STEM. Following from this, the paper explains how findings of the review led to the generation of an emergent theoretical framework and concludes by offering suggestions for how this framework may address the needs of practitioners and policy makers.

Lesson Study

LS, which originated in Japan over one hundred years ago, involves an action cycle whereby a group of teachers collaboratively plan, teach, observe and reflect on a research lesson taught with a group of pupils (Lewis, et al., 2006). Previous research has suggested that LS is effective in enhancing teachers' pedagogical skills and knowledge as part of curriculum reform (e.g. Ní Shúilleabháin & Seery, 2018); in fostering teachers' collaborative practice (e.g. Dudley et al., 2019; Lewanowski-Breen et al., 2020); and in supporting the development of positive teacher efficacy beliefs (e.g. Chong & Kong, 2012; Schipper et al., 2020). Seleznyov (2018) examined the fidelity of various adapted LS interventions in different jurisdictions. Their study identified seven critical components which are required in order for an LS intervention to be successful in enhancing teachers' learning:

1. The identification of a broad goal for pupil learning;
2. Teacher planning in collaborative groups drawing on relevant research and resources to create a research lesson;
3. A research lesson taught by one group member and observed by the others;
4. A post-lesson discussion using conversation protocols;
5. Repeated cycles of research using the findings from the post-lesson discussion;
6. The support of an outside expert or Knowledgeable Other (KO) throughout the process;
7. Opportunities for sharing new knowledge outside the LS group, for example, with other colleagues in their own or in other schools.

For the purpose of this paper, these seven critical components of LS as described by Seleznyov (2018) are adopted as a conceptual framework in order to examine existing studies related to LS.

Teacher Agency

Within the context of the draft Primary Curriculum Framework, an agentic teacher is described as “reflective, competent and capable of exercising professional judgement in response to individual learning needs in a variety of contexts” (NCCA, 2020, p. 6). Biesta and Tedder (2006, p.137) suggest that agency is not something teachers have, rather it is something which is achieved “by means of their environment”. Similarly, Priestly et al. (2015) describe agency as an “emergent phenomenon of the ecological conditions through which it is enacted” (p.22). Furthermore, as Scanlon et al. (2020) contend, the achievement of agency cannot be considered static, but rather occurs on a processual basis, fluctuating from minute-to-minute, and is contingent on a complex myriad of factors. Thus, this paper adopts an ecological conceptualisation of teacher agency, according to which, achievement of agency derives from the complex interplay of individual efforts, available resources, contextual and

structural factors as they converge in particular and unique ways (Priestly et al., 2015). In line with this conceptualisation of agency as ecologically constructed, this paper is underpinned by the view that agency is temporal, i.e. constructed based on the past (iterational), enacted in the present (practical-evaluative) and oriented towards the future (projective) (Emirbayer & Mische, 1998; Priestly et al., 2015). Agency-enabling factors include school cultures which feature strong horizontal relationships between colleagues, characterised by collegiality and sharing of practice (Poulton, 2020). Such cultures which emphasise teacher autonomy and professional judgement more broadly, rather than an overemphasis on accountability can also support teachers' achievement of agency.

Research Design and Methodological Approach

Given the focus on teacher agency, the review design was underpinned by a pragmatic epistemological orientation, which sought to ensure that the voices, views and lived experiences of teachers were represented in the included studies. A search protocol was prepared prior to commencing the search process, which included broad search terms, arranged according to three strands pertaining to LS: "Lesson study" and "agency"; "Lesson study" and "primary" or "elementary"; and "Lesson study" and "mathematics", "science" or "STEM". These terms were used to conduct a preliminary search of existing literature which returned over 3000 studies. Basic search limits were then set to include studies which focused on practicing teachers rather than preservice teachers; academic articles with full text accessible via electronic databases and articles which were published in English. Limits were also set to include studies from 2000 onwards, in order to focus on the most up-to-date research in relation to LS (Hennessy et al., 2019). The terms outlined in the search protocol were used to create search strings for each area of focus which were input to electronic databases Scopus, Education Source and Web of Science. Manual searches were then conducted of relevant conference proceedings as well as recent issues of *International Journal of Lesson and Learning Studies (IJLS)* towards the end of the literature retrieval process to ensure that the most current studies had been included. Reference lists from prior reviews were also checked in order to identify older seminal studies (Booth, 2016). Titles of returned studies were screened to remove duplicates. Abstracts of the remaining studies were then screened to retain only those which were relevant to the research question.

As the review sought to include studies from qualitative and quantitative domains, a quantitative critical appraisal checklist and qualitative critical appraisal checklist were designed and the relevant checklist was applied to returned studies (Hannes, 2011; Moher et al., 2009). These checklists were used to systematically examine research evidence to assess validity and relevance of their findings. The main reasons for exclusion of studies were that they were theoretical in nature, provided insufficient detail regarding the nature of the activities conducted during the LS or were not from the perspective of teachers. Following appraisal, data from included studies were then extracted. This data included the context, research design and findings from the study, as well as direct quotes from teachers involved in studies. These data were then thematically analysed (Braun & Clarke, 2006) by deductive

and inductive coding of instances where agency was constrained or enabled, as reported by participants.

Findings and Discussion

Following a process of identification, screening and critical appraisal, a total of 32 studies were deemed eligible for inclusion in the review. Thematic analysis of data from these studies were recorded as codes which were arranged under two categories: agency enablers and agency constrainters. For the purpose of the present paper, the focus will be placed on agency enablers derived from LS activities. While the research question sought to identify instances of agency enablement in the separate context of primary STEM, what emerged from the examination of findings from the included studies was that the factors which contributed to agency were not subject specific, rather these factors appeared to be common across multiple contexts in both primary and STEM. For the purpose of this paper, a summary of findings pertaining to agency enablers will be reported using illustrative quotes from some of the selected studies.

Agency enablers which were identified during LS activities were categorised as access to Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK), professional community membership and collaborative expertise. PCK describes the unique knowledge of curriculum, pupils and pedagogical strategies which are required for effective teaching (Shulman, 1987). Regarding PCK, for example, findings from one study (Coenders & Verhoef, 2019, p.228) noted that “going through complete Lesson Study cycles results in teachers realizing and internalizing new PCK and beliefs”. Professional community membership describes the way in which the structured protocols of LS helps to create a sociocultural learning space for teachers, where they learn through engaging in critical reflective dialogue (Dudley et al., 2019). An example of this was evident in findings in another study (Brosnan, 2014, p.241), which speak of the “insulation and isolation” experienced by teachers which is ameliorated through engaging with other teachers and KOs in LS. In the case a further study (Chong & Kong, 2012), teacher learning in LS was attributed to “the constant collegial collaborative interactions between participants and KOs” (Baricaua Gutierrez, 2018, p.813), which suggests such interactions foster agency under the category of collaborative expertise (Dudley et al., 2019).

Towards an Emergent Framework

Taking the enabling factors of PCK, professional community membership and collaborative expertise, Figure One aims to make explicit how the specific activities carried out as part of LS might foster each of the temporal dimensions of agency (Emirbayer & Mische, 1998; Priestly et al., 2015). While each enabling factor has been separated here for clarity, it is important to note that there is a degree of overlap, i.e. certain LS activities contribute to both PCK and professional community membership, for example, post-lesson reflective discussions. Within the framework, an overlap across temporal dimensions can also be seen, for example, the uncovering of tacit knowledge and beliefs spans both iterational, practical-evaluative and projective dimensions.

Figure 1

Emergent theoretical framework linking LS activities to temporal dimensions of teacher agency.

Agency enabler	<i>Access to Pedagogical Content Knowledge</i>		
Dimension of agency →	Iterational	Practical-evaluative	Projective
Phase of LS cycle☒			
Formulate goal	Tacit prior knowledge and beliefs about pedagogy and classroom practices uncovered		
Research & plan	Tacit prior knowledge, skills and experiences pertaining to overarching goal are drawn from participants by the K.O.	K.O. facilitates critical reflection on relevant research linked to area of focus of research lesson	Research lesson is planned with pupil responses and outcomes anticipated
Teach & Observe	Focused teaching and observation on pupil interaction with planned tasks which are documented in order to inform post-lesson discussion		
Reflect & Evaluate	Critically reflective dialogue facilitated by K.O., focused on taught research lesson, using the new knowledge generated to inform future teaching/ next LS cycle		

Agency enabler	<i>Access to Collaborative Expertise</i>		
Dimension of agency →	Iterational	Practical-evaluative	Projective
Phase of LS cycle☒			
Formulate goal	Tacit prior knowledge and beliefs about pedagogy and classroom practices uncovered, in order to identify learning outcomes		
Research & plan	Tacit prior knowledge, skills and experiences pertaining to overarching goal are drawn from participants by the K.O		
Teach & Observe	Opportunity to observe a colleague teaching, with focus on taught lesson and pupils' learning rather than on the person		
Reflect & Evaluate	Critically reflective dialogue facilitated by K.O., focused on taught research lesson, using the new knowledge generated to inform future teaching/ next LS cycle		

Agency enabler	<i>Access to Professional Community Membership</i>		
Dimension of agency →	Iterational	Practical-evaluative	Projective
Phase of LS cycle☒			
Formulate goal	Safe environment created by use of structured LS protocols-encourages uncovering of tacit beliefs ,	Establishment and strengthening of horizontal relationships	Discussion and sharing of variety of perspectives on purposes of
Research & plan			
Teach & Observe			

Reflect & Evaluate	knowledge and experiences in relation to pedagogy and classroom practices	between teachers within the LS group	education and broad vision for pupil outcomes
-------------------------------	---	--------------------------------------	---

Limitations

A limitation deriving from features described in the framework is that they are relatively broad in nature, and may not be applicable to LS in every context. However, the emergent framework serves an important purpose, in that it has contributed to establishing a theoretical connection between agency and LS, which did not previously exist.

Implications

While this review sought to examine how and in what circumstances LS can enable teacher agency in the context of primary STEM, what emerged was that insufficient literature was available to examine LS and agency in this specific context. This highlights that despite LS receiving much scholarly attention, further empirical research is required in order to examine how these LS may contribute to, or indeed constrain, teacher agency.

The findings of this review have enabled the development of an emergent theoretical framework which seeks to make explicit how LS can contribute to teachers' achievement of agency. Due to its purely theoretical nature, the emergent framework would benefit from further application and testing in the field, for example, by teacher practitioners using it to support critical professional reflection on their own achievement of agency during LS. The framework may also be useful for LS facilitators who wish to foster teacher agency as part of their practice. It may also be useful for policy makers engaged in curricular reform, who may find the framework useful in guiding LS as a PD approach in the context of such reform.

References

- Baricaua Gutierrez, S. (2016). Building a classroom-based professional learning community through lesson study: Insights from elementary school science teachers. *Professional Development in Education*, 42(5), 801-817.
- Biesta, G., & Tedder, M. (2006). *How is agency possible? Towards an ecological understanding of agency-as-achievement. Learning lives: Learning, identity, and agency in the life course*. Working paper. University of Exeter.
- Booth, A. (2016). Searching for qualitative research for inclusion in systematic reviews: A structured methodological review. *Systematic Reviews*, 5(1), 74-97.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77-101.
- Brosnan, A. (2014). Introducing lesson study in promoting a new mathematics curriculum in Irish post-primary schools. *International Journal for Lesson and Learning Studies*, 3(3), 236-251.
- Chong, W. H., & Kong, C. A. (2012). Teacher collaborative learning and teacher self-efficacy: The case of lesson study. *Journal of Experimental Education*, 80(3), 263-283.

- Coenders, F., & Verhoef, N. (2019). Lesson study: Professional development (PD) for beginning and experienced teachers. *Professional Development in Education*, 45(2), 217-230.
- Darling-Hammond, L. (2005). Teaching as a profession: Lessons in teacher preparation and professional development. *Phi Delta Kappan*, 87(3), 237-240.
- Department of Education and Skills (DES). (2016). *STEM Education Policy Statement 2017-2026*. Retrieved 10th May 2019 <https://www.education.ie/en/The-Education-System/STEM-Education-Policy/stem-education-policy-statement-2017-2026-.pdf>
- Dudley, P., Xu, H., Vermunt, J. D., & Lang, J. (2019). Empirical evidence of the impact of lesson study on students' achievement, teachers' professional learning and on institutional and system evolution. *European Journal of Education*, 54(2), 202-217.
- Emirbayer, M., & Mische, A. (1998). What is agency? *American Journal of Sociology*, 103(4), 962-1023.
- Eteläpelto, A., Vähäsantanen, K., Hökkä, P., & Paloniemi, S. (2013). What is agency? Conceptualizing professional agency at work. *Educational Research Review*, 10, 45-65.
- Godfrey, D., Seleznyov, S., Anders, J., Wollaston, N., & Barrera-Pedemonte, F. (2019). A developmental evaluation approach to lesson study: Exploring the impact of lesson study in London schools. *Professional Development in Education*, 45(2), 325-340.
- Groves, S., Doig, B., Vale, C., & Widjaja, W. (2016). Critical factors in the adaptation and implementation of Japanese lesson study in the Australian context. *ZDM*, 48(4), 501-512.
- Hadfield, M., & Jopling, M. (2016). Problematizing lesson study and its impacts: Studying a highly contextualised approach to professional learning. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 60, 203-214.
- Hannes, K. (2011). Critical appraisal of qualitative research. In Noyes, J., Booth, A., Hannes, K., Harden, A., Harris, J., Lewin, S., & Lockwood, C. (Eds.). *Supplementary Guidance for Inclusion of Qualitative Research in Cochrane Systematic Reviews of Interventions*. Version 1. Retrieved 6th May 2020 <http://cqrng.cochrane.org/supplemental-handbook-guidance>
- Hennessy, E. A., Johnson, B. T., & Keenan, C. (2019). Best practice guidelines and essential methodological steps to conduct rigorous and systematic meta-reviews. *Applied Psychology: Health and Well-Being*, 11(3), 353-381.
- Lewanowski-Breen, E., Shuilleabhain, A. N., & Meehan, M. (2020). Lesson study and the long-term impact on teacher professional community development. *International Journal for Lesson & Learning Studies*, 10(1), 89-101.
- Lewis, C., Perry, R. & Murata, A. (2006). How should research contribute to instructional improvement? The case of lesson study. *Educational Researcher*, 35(3), 3-14.
- Moher, D., Liberati, A., Tetzlaff, J. & Altman, D. (2009). Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: the PRISMA statement. *PloS Medicine*, 6(7), 1-6.

- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA). (2020). *Draft primary curriculum framework*. Retrieved 6th July 2020 <https://ncca.ie/media/4456/ncca-primary-curriculum-framework-2020.pdf>
- Ní Shuilleabháin, A., & Seery, A. (2018). Enacting curriculum reform through lesson study: A case study of mathematics teacher learning. *Professional Development in Education*, 44(2), 222-236.
- Poulton, P. (2020). Teacher agency in curriculum reform: the role of assessment in enabling and constraining primary teachers' agency. *Curriculum Perspectives*, 40(1), 35-48.
- Priestly, M., Biesta, G. & Robinson, S. (2015). *Teacher agency: An ecological approach*. Bloomsbury.
- Rosicka, C. (2016). *From concept to classroom: Translating STEM education research into practice*. Australian Council for Educational Research (ACER).
- Scanlon, D., Calderon, A., & MacPhail, A. (2020). Teacher agency in enacting physical education in a period of curriculum change and reform in Ireland. *The Curriculum Journal*, 32(1), 48-66. Retrieved from <https://bera-journals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/curj.80>
- Schipper, T. M., de Vries, S., Goei, S. L., & van Veen, K. (2020). Promoting a professional school culture through lesson study? An examination of school culture, school conditions, and teacher self-efficacy. *Professional Development in Education*, 46(1), 112-129.
- Shulman, L. (1987). Knowledge and teaching: Foundations of the new reform. *Harvard Educational Review*, 57(1), 1-23.
- Seleznyov, S. (2018). Lesson study: An exploration of its translation beyond Japan. *International Journal for Lesson and Learning Studies*, 7(3), 217-229.